

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
ON
FORMATION OF THE EUROPEAN CONSORTIUM
FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE
DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM OF SCIENTIFIC COLLECTIONS (DiSSCo)
Amended version
(16 October, 2020)

This Memorandum of Understanding on Formation of the European Consortium for Participation in the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (hereinafter "European MoU") is signed by 41 signatories formally representing (through national agreements in place and referenced hereinto) [177] participating organisations across [23] countries:

- 1) University of Tartu, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-EE-NATCON*) representing the **Estonia** national consortium of **four organisations**: (i) University of Tartu, (ii) Tallinn University of Technology, (iii) Estonian University of Life Sciences, (iv) Estonian Museum of Natural History.
- 2) Swedish Museum of Natural History, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-SE.NATCON*) representing the **Sweden** national consortium of **eight organisations**: (i) Swedish Museum of Natural History, (ii) Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Gothenburg, (iii) Gothenburg Botanical Garden, Västra Götalandsregionen, (iv) The Gothenburg Museum of Natural History, Västra Götalandsregionen, (v) Bergius Foundation, (vi) Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University, (vii) Department of Biology, Lund University, (viii) Department of Ecology and Environmental Science, Umeå University.
- 3) Finnish Museum of Natural History, University of Helsinki, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-FI-NATCON*) representing the **Finland** national consortium of **seven organisations**: (i) Finnish Museum of Natural History 'Luomus', University of Helsinki, (ii) Biodiversity Unit, University of Turku, (iii) Biodiversity Unit, University of Oulu, (iv) Open Science Centre / Museum, University of Jyväskylä, (v) Kuopio Natural History Museum, (vi) Digitarium, (vii) Finnish Environment Institute, SYKE.
- 4) University of Lisbon, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-PT-NATCON*) representing the **Portugal** national consortium of **three organisations**: (i) University of Lisbon, (ii) University of Coimbra, (iii) University of Porto.
- 5) National Museum, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-CZ-NATCON*) representing the **Czech Republic** national consortium of **six organisations**: (i) National Museum, (ii) Charles University, Faculty of Science, (iii) Masaryk University, (iv) Institute of Botany, The Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic, (v) Institute of Vertebrate Biology, The Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic, (vi) Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic.
- 6) The Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), duly (*DISSCO-MOU-ES NATCON*) representing the **Spain** national consortium of **six**

- organisations:** (i) The Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), (ii) Universidad de Navarra (UNED), (iii) Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME), (iv) Universidad Complutense de Madrid, (v) Museu d'Història Natural and Jardí Botànic, Universitat de València, (vi) Consorci del Museu de Ciències Natural de Barcelona (CMCNB).
- 7) Natural History Museum of Crete, University of Crete, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-GR-NATCON*) representing the **Greece** national consortium of **thirteen organisations:** (i) Natural History Museum of Crete – University of Crete, (ii) Museum of Zoology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, (iii) Museum of Geology-Palaeontology-Palaeoanthropology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki School of Geology, (iv) Zoological Museum, University of Patras, (v) Botanical Museum, University of Patras, (vi) Department of Geology, University of Patras, (vii) Botanical Museum and Herbarium, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, (viii) Museum of Zoology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, (ix) Museum of Geology and Palaeontology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, (x) Mineralogy and Petrology Museum, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, (xi) Goulandris Natural History Museum, (xii) Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Chania, (xiii) Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest.
- 8) Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università degli Studi di Firenze, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-IT-NATCON*) representing the **Italy** national consortium of **nine organisations:** (i) Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche-CNR (ii) Associazione Nazionale Musei Scientifici, (iii) Accademia Nazionale delle Scienze, (iv) Accademia Nazionale di Entomologia, (v) Società Botanica Italiana, (vi) Società Geologica Italiana, (vii) Società Paleontologica Italiana, (viii) Società Italiana di Biogeografia, (ix) Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università degli Studi di Firenze.
- 9) Centrum biológie rastlín a biodiverzity, Botanický ústav Slovenskej akadémie vied, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-Slovakia-NATCON*) representing the **Slovakia** national consortium of **three organisations:** (i) Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave, (ii) Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Šafárika v Košiciach, (iii) Centrum biológie rastlín a biodiverzity, Botanický ústav Slovenskej akadémie vied.
- 10) Natural History Museum of Denmark, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-DK-NATCON*) representing the **Denmark** national consortium of **three organisations:** (i) Natural History Museum of Denmark, University of Copenhagen, (ii) Natural History Museum Aarhus, (iii) The Science Museums, Aarhus University.
- 11) Naturalis Biodiversity Center duly (*DISSCO-MOU-NL-NATCON*) representing **The Netherlands** national consortium of **fourteen organisations:** (i) Naturalis Biodiversity Center, (ii) Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute, (iii) University of Amsterdam – LifeWatch NL, (iv) Stichting NLBIF, Netherlands Biodiversity Information Facility, (v) Stichting Museum, (vi) Utrecht University Museum, (vii) Stichting De Bastei, (viii) De Museumfabriek (voorheen Stichting TwentseWelle), (ix) Teylers Museum, (x) Natuurhistorisch Museum Rotterdam, (xi) Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, (xii) NIOZ Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research, (xiii) Natuurmuseum Brabant, (xiv) Natuurmuseum Fryslân.
- 12) Natural History Museum, University of Oslo, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-NO-NATCON*)

representing the **Norway** national consortium of **four organisations**: (i) Natural History Museum, University of Oslo, (ii) NTNU University Museum, Norwegian Museum of Science and Technology, (iii) University Museum of Bergen, University of Bergen, (iv) Arctic University Museum of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway.

- 13) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IBER-BAS), duly (*DISSCO-MOU-BG-NATCON*) representing the **Bulgaria** national consortium of **two organisations**: (i) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IBER-BAS), (ii) National Museum of Natural History, Sofia – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NMNHS-BAS).
- 14) Muséum national d'histoire naturelle duly (*DISSCO-MOU-FR-NATCON*) representing the **France** national consortium of **twenty nine organisations**: (i) Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, (ii) Conservatoire botanique national Alpin, (iii) Université de Strasbourg, (iv) Tela Botanica, (v) Université de Rennes 1, (vi) Université de Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier, (vii) Sorbonne Université, (viii) Société National des Sciences Naturelles et Mathématiques de Cherbourg, (ix) Centre Informatique National de l'Enseignement Supérieur, (x) Université Clermont Auvergne, (xi) Muséum d'histoire naturelle Philadelphie-Thomas de Gaillac, (xii) Le Jardin Botanique de la Ville de Lyon, (xiii) Université de Montpellier, (xiv) Université Lille 1 – Sciences et technologies, (xv) Université de Bourgogne, (xvi) Institut Recherche et Développement, (xvii) Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement, (xviii) Université Claude-Bernard Lyon 1, (xix) Muséum d'histoire naturelle de La Rochelle, (xx) Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Dijon, (xxi) Université Aix-Marseille, (xxii) Muséum Aquarium de Nancy, (xxiii) Université de Lorraine, (xxiv) Université de Grenoble, (xxv) Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Marseille, (xxvi) Musée d'histoire naturelle de Lille, (xxvii) Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Toulouse, (xxviii) Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Nantes, (xxix) Office de l'environnement de Corse / Conservatoire botanique national de Corse.
- 15) Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, **Belgium**
- 16) Agentschap Plantentuin Meise, **Belgium**
- 17) Royal Museum of Central Africa, Tervuren, **Belgium**
- 18) Natural History Museum, London, **United Kingdom**
- 19) Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF AISBL), Brussels, **Belgium**
- 20) Naturhistorisches Museum Wien/Museum of Natural History Vienna, **Austria**
- 21) Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO), **Belgium**
- 22) Université Libre de Bruxelles, **Belgium**
- 23) Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ)/Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ), **Belgium**
- 24) Royal Zoological Society of Antwerp, **Belgium**

- 25) Université de Namur/University of Namur, **Belgium**
- 26) Botanischer Garten und Botanisches Museum, Freie Universität Berlin, **Germany**
- 27) Museum für Naturkunde, Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Berlin, **Germany**
- 28) Leibniz-Institut zur Analyse des Biodiversitätswandels (LIB)/Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change (LIB), **Germany**
- 29) Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns (SNSB)-Bavarian Natural History Collections, **Germany**
- 30) Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung, **Germany**
- 31) Hungarian Natural History Museum, **Hungary**
- 32) Musée national d'histoire naturelle de Luxembourg (MnhnL), **Luxembourg**
- 33) The University of Warsaw, duly (*DISSCO-MOU-PL-NATCON*) representing the **Poland** national consortium of **two organisations**: (i) The University of Warsaw, Poland, (ii) Museum and Institute of Zoology PAS.
- 34) Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh, **United Kingdom**
- 35) Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, **United Kingdom**
- 36) Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttgart, **Germany**
- 37) National Natural History Collection, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, duly (*DiSSCo_MOU_IL_NATCON*) representing the **Israel** national consortium of **four organisations**: (i) The National Natural History Collection, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, (ii) Beit Margolin Zoological Collection – Oranim, Academic College Education, (iii) Geological Survey of Israel, (iv) University of Haifa – The Research Authority representing the Natural Science Collections.
- 38) Musnatcoll duly (*DISSCO-MOU-Swiss NATCON*) representing the **Switzerland** national consortium of **thirty six organisations**: (i) Naturama Aargau, (ii) Stadt Zofingen, Naturhistorische Abteilung Museum, (iii) Botanischer Garten Bern, (iv) Naturhistorisches Museum Bern, (v) Museum BL, (vi) Naturhistorisches Museum Basel, (vii) Herbarien Basel, (viii) 8. Musée d'histoire naturelle Fribourg, (ix) Musée d'histoire naturelle Genève, (x) Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de la ville de Genève, (xi) Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen des Kantons Glarus, (xii) Bündner Naturmuseum, (xiii) Jurassica Museum, (xiv) Natur-Museum Luzern, (xv) Musée d'histoire naturelle La Chaux-de-Fonds, (xvi) Musée d'histoire naturelle Neuchâtel, (xvii) Noeud GBIF Suisse, (xviii) Naturmuseum St. Gallen, (xix) Museum zu Allerheiligen, (xx) Naturmuseum Olten, (xxi) Naturmuseum Solothurn, (xxii) Naturmuseum Thurgau, (xxiii) Museo Cantonale di Storia naturale Lugano, (xxiv) Musée de Géologie Lausanne, (xxv) Musée de Zoologie Lausanne, (xxvi) Anthropologisches Institut und Museum der Universität Zürich, (xxvii) Botanisches Museum der Universität

Zürich, (xxviii) Entomologische Sammlung der ETH Zürich, (xxix) *focus*Terra ETH Zürich, (xxx) Sukkulanten-Sammlung Zürich, (xxxi) KULTURAMA Museum des Menschen, (xxxii) Naturmuseum Winterthur, (xxxiii) Paläontologisches Institut und Museum der Universität Zürich, (xxxiv) Sauriermuseum Aathal, (xxxv) Zoologisches Museum der Universität Zürich, (xxxvi) Stiftung Wildnispark Zürich.

39) Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), **Belgium**

40) KU Leuven - University of Leuven, **Belgium**

41) UGent - University of Ghent, **Belgium**

Hereinafter the 'Signatories'.

WHEREAS

- Natural sciences collections are an integral part of the European natural and cultural capital. For maximising the value and impact of European natural science collections it is critical that collection facilities constitute a unified European research infrastructure to provide seamless access to the information, expertise and knowledge linked to collections held across Europe. By doing so, European collections will transform into an advanced, global and open structure that could then act as the necessary pillar that underpins scientific excellence and industrial innovation, in response to societal challenges;
- Natural science collection-based organisations from the same country are formulating National Consortia for participation in the European DiSSCo;
- The agreed scientific rationale and design principles of the DiSSCo research infrastructure are described in Annex A (DiSSCo high-level summary of concept and approach) of this European MoU;
- The commonly agreed modalities upon the planned governance, management and participation modalities are described in Annex B (Governance, management and participation model for DiSSCo implementation and operation) of this European MoU;
- The signatories of the EU MoU benefit from the experience of multiple collaborations through national and European funded projects. A number of EU signatories participate as beneficiaries in three main DiSSCo-linked projects. The Distributed System of Scientific Collections - Preparatory Phase Project - No. 871043 (DiSSCo Prepare) focused in delivery key outputs to reach the maturity necessary for the Research Infrastructure to enter successfully in the construction phase and secondly, the fourth iteration of SYNTHESYS programme (SYNTHESYS+) which objective is to deliver key outputs to speed up the digital mobilisation and access to the natural history collections, and Mobilise (Cost Action CA17106) that aims to mobilise data, policies and experts in Scientific Collections;
- The acceptance of DiSSCo onto the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Roadmap in 2018 has made European Natural Science Collection a recognised priority research infrastructure;

- The transition into the preparatory phase requires certain adjustments to the original European MoU.

Therefore, the Signatories hereby agree as follows:

Article 1
PURPOSE AND NATURE OF AGREEMENT

- (1) The purpose of this European MoU is to formulate the European Consortium of the Distributed System of Scientific Collections, for the purposes of working together towards the successful implementation of the preparatory, and subsequent transition phases of DiSSCo Research Infrastructure until DiSSCo legal entity is constituted and is in operation.
- (2) Nothing in this European MoU is deemed to constitute an agency or any kind of formal grouping or entity between the Signatories.
- (3) Nothing in this European MoU is deemed to constitute binding obligation among the signatories and/or towards any third party under the national or international public law.
- (4) The Signatories agree not to withhold information that is relevant to the implementation of this European MoU.

Article 2
TERMS OF PARTICIPATION

- (1) Each Signatory participates on an equal basis to the group of Signatories, hereinafter referred to as the 'DiSSCo Consortium'.
- (2) Signatories representing a national consortium of participating organisations from the same country, sign this European MoU on behalf of and in agreement with their national consortium members. Where such consortia agreements exist, they automatically become reference material of this European MoU.
- (3) Signatories from countries that have not yet set up a national consortium sign this European MoU on their own behalf as a single organisation.
- (4) CETAF signs this European MoU on behalf of CETAF member institutions.
- (5) The Signatories have adopted specific Terms of Reference for the General Assembly during the preparatory and transition phase of DiSSCo.

Article 3
ACCESSION

- (1) The DiSSCo Consortium will pursue an inclusive approach to this European MoU, aiming at

the enlargement of the Consortium with new stakeholders.

- (2) For each new party to join the Consortium, a formal agreement, on the basis of this European MoU, is required.

Article 4
REPRESENTATION

- (1) The DiSSCo Consortium recognises the coordinating role of the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office, as described in Annex C (Responsibilities and membership of the DiSSCo Proposal Coordination and Support Office), and as may be further developed in the Terms of Reference for the General Assembly or related documents.

Article 5
ENTRY INTO FORCE AND TERMINATION

- (1) This amended European MoU shall come into effect between the Signatories as of the date of the fourth signature. It comes into effect for each additional Signatory after the said date as of the date of signature by the said additional Signatory.
- (2) Subject to agreement by more than 50% of the Signatories, the DiSSCo Consortium may decide to terminate this European MoU. In such a case, the Signatories deciding on the termination shall inform the other Signatories in writing, subject to a three-month prior notification. The remaining Signatories may decide that the European MoU shall remain effective between them (provided that at least two Signatories remain).
- (3) The Articles and paragraphs of this European MoU may be reviewed by the General Assembly of the Signatories, following its inaugural meeting.

Article 6
AMENDMENT AND ASSIGNMENT

- (1) Except for additional Signatories to this European MoU, any modification requires the written and signed consent of all the Signatories hereto to become effective.
- (2) No rights or obligations of any of the Signatories arising from this European MoU may be assigned or transferred in whole or in part to any third party without the explicit and written consent of the other Signatories.
- (3) The Annexes of this European MoU form an integral part thereof.

Article 7
LANGUAGE

- (1) This European MoU is drawn up in English, the language which governs all documents,

notices, meetings and processes relative hereto.

SIGNATURES

This Memorandum of Understanding includes seven (7) Articles and three (3) Annexes, signed, by the duly authorised undersigned representatives in [41] identical original copies. One copy is retained by each of the Signatories and one copy is forwarded to the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office for its acknowledgement and further relations at the following address, that will retain it:

DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office
c/o Dimitris Koureas
Naturalis Biodiversity Center
Darwinweg 2, 2333 CR Leiden
The Netherlands

ESTONIA

Name of the Signatory Organisation: UNIVERSITY OF TARTU

Name of the Organisation's representative: Kristjan Vassil

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 3 December 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the ESTONIAN national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. University of Tartu
2. Tallinn University of Technology
3. Estonian University of Life Sciences
4. Estonian Museum of Natural History

For country-level Consortia

Sweden

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Swedish Museum of Natural History

Name of the Organisation's representative: Director General Dr. Joakim Malmström

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 17 December, 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the Swedish national Consortium of the following Organisations:

**Naturhistoriska
riksmuseet**

1. Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Gothenburg
2. Gothenburg Botanical Garden, Västra Götalandsregionen
3. The Gothenburg Museum of Natural History, Västra Götalandsregionen
4. Bergius Foundation, Stockholm
5. Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University
6. Department of Biology, Lund University,
7. Department of Ecology and Environmental Science, Umeå University

...

For country-level Consortia

Finland

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Finnish Museum of Natural History 'Luomus'

Name of the Organisation's representative: Leif Schulman

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: Espoo, Finland, 30 November 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the Finland national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Finnish Museum of Natural History 'Luomus', University of Helsinki,
2. Biodiversity Unit, University of Turku
3. Biodiversity Unit, University of Oulu
4. Open Science Centre / Museum, University of Jyväskylä
5. Kuopio Natural History Museum

For country-level Consortia

PORTUGAL

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Universidade de Lisboa

Name of the Organisation's representative: António Manuel da Cruz Serra

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

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Digital Qualificada por:
ANTÓNIO MANUEL DA CRUZ
SERRA
Universidade de Lisboa
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Date: _____

The Signatory Organisation represents the PORTUGAL national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Universidade de Lisboa
2. Universidade de Coimbra
3. Universidade do Porto

For country-level Consortia

CZECH REPUBLIC

Name of the Signatory Organisation: National Museum / Národní muzeum,
Václavské náměstí 1700/68, Praha 1

Name of the Organisation's representative: PhDr. Michal Lukeš, Ph.D., Director General

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 28. 12. 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the CZECH REPUBLIC national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Charles University, Faculty of science
2. Masaryk University
3. National Museum
4. Institute of Botany, The Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic
5. Institute of Vertebrate Biology, The Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic
6. Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic

SPAIN

Name of the Signatory Organisation: The Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Santiago Merino Rodriguez

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

MERINO RODRIGUEZ
SANTIAGO - DNI 50826715G

Firmado digitalmente por MERINO RODRIGUEZ SANTIAGO - DNI 50826715G
Nombre del reconocimiento (DNI): e-ES-CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE
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ou=50826715, serialNumber=50826715G, ou=MERINO RODRIGUEZ,
givenName=SANTIAGO, cn=MERINO RODRIGUEZ SANTIAGO - DNI
50826715G
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Date: _____

The Signatory Organisation represents the SPAIN national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. The Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
2. The Universidad de Navarra (UNED)
3. The Instituto Geológico y Minero (IGME)

Greece

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Natural History Museum of Crete – University of Crete

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Nikos Poulakakis

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

NIKOLAOS
POULAKAKIS

Digitally signed
by Nikolaos
Poulakakis
Date: 2021.02.03
14:04:35 +02'00'

Date: 3 February 2021

The Signatory Organisation represents the Greek national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Natural History Museum of Crete, University of Crete, duly represented by Poulakakis Nikolaos.
2. Museum of Zoology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, duly represented by Chintiroglou Chariton.
3. Museum of Geology-Palaeontology-Palaeoanthropology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki School of Geology, duly represented by Kostopoulos Dimitris.
4. Zoological Museum, University of Patras, duly represented by Sinos Giokas.
5. Botanical Museum, University of Patras, duly represented by Dimopoulos Panayotis.
6. Department of Geology, University of Patras, duly represented by Iliopoulos George.
7. Botanical Museum and Herbarium, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, duly represented by Constantinidis Theophanis.
8. Museum of Zoology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, duly represented by Valakos Efstratios.
9. Museum of Geology and Palaeontology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, duly represented by Koskeridou Efterpi.
10. Mineralogy and Petrology Museum, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, duly represented by Voudouris Panagiotis.
11. Goulandris Natural History Museum, duly represented by Dimaki Maria.
12. Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Chania, duly represented by Baourakis Georgios.
13. Natural History Museum of the Lesvos Petrified Forest, duly represented by Zouros Nikolaos.

For country-level Consortia

ITALY

Name of the Signatory Organisation: **Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università degli Studi di Firenze**

Name of the Organisation's representative: *prof. Marco Benvenuti*

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M Benvenuti', is written over a horizontal line.

Date: November 2nd, 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the **Italian** national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche-CNR
2. Associazione Nazionale Musei Scientifici
3. Accademia Nazionale delle Scienze
4. Accademia Nazionale di Entomologia
5. Società Botanica Italiana
6. Società Geologica Italiana
7. Società Paleontologica Italiana
8. Società Italiana di Biogeografia
9. Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università degli Studi di Firenze

SLOVAKIA

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Centrum biológie rastlín a biodiverzity, Botanický ústav Slovenskej akadémie vied

Name of the Organisation's representative: Mgr. Anna Bérešová, PhD.

Signature of the Organisation's representative: Anna Bérešová Digitálne podepsal Anna Bérešová
Datum: 2020.11.02 08:55:59
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Date: 2. 11.2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the SLOVAK national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Univerzita Komenského v Bratislave
2. Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Šafárika v Košiciach
3. Centrum biológie rastlín a biodiverzity, Botanický ústav Slovenskej akadémie vied

For country-level Consortia

DENMARK

Name of the Signatory Organisation: University of Copenhagen

Name of the Organisation's representative: Rector Henrik C. Wegener

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: December 15 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the **danish** national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Natural History Museum of Denmark, University of Copenhagen
2. The Science Museums, Aarhus University
3. Natural History Museum Aarhus

Country-level Consortium

The Netherlands

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Naturalis Biodiversity Center

Name of the Organisation's representative: Edwin van Huis

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of a large, stylized 'E' followed by a horizontal line and a small flourish.

Date: 3 December 2020

The Signatory Organisation represents the Netherlands national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Naturalis Biodiversity Center,
2. Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute,
3. University of Amsterdam – LifeWatch NL,
4. Stichting NLBIF, Netherlands Biodiversity Information Facility,
5. Stichting Museon,
6. Utrecht University Museum,
7. Stichting De Bastei,
8. De Museumfabriek (voorheen Stichting TwentseWelle),
9. Teylers Museum,
10. Natuurhistorisch Museum Rotterdam,
11. Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht,
12. NIOZ Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research,
13. Natuurmuseum Brabant,
14. Natuurmuseum Fryslân.

For country-level Consortia

Norway

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Natural History Museum, University of Oslo

Name of the Organisation's representative: Hugo de Boer

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Hugo de Boer', is written over a horizontal line.

Date: February 5th 2021

The Signatory Organisation represents the Norwegian national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Natural History Museum, University of Oslo
2. NTNU University Museum, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
3. University Museum of Bergen, University of Bergen
4. Arctic University Museum of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway

BULGARIA

Name of the Signatory Organisation:

**Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IBER-BAS)
[INSTITUT PO BIORAZNOOBRAZIE I EKOSISTEMNI IZSLEDVANIYA BALGARSKA
AKADEMIYA NA NAUKITE]**

Name of the Organisation's representative: **Boyko Bozhidarov GEORGIEV**

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: **February 5th, 2021**

The Signatory Organisation represents the Bulgaria national Consortium of the following Organisations:

- 1. Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IBER-BAS)**
- 2. National Museum of Natural History, Sofia – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NMNHS-BAS)**

FRANCE Consortium (RECOLNAT)

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Muséum national d'histoire naturelle (MNHN)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Bruno DAVID, President

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 16 FEB. 2021

The Signatory Organisation represents the France national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. Muséum national d'histoire naturelle
2. Conservatoire botanique national Alpin
3. Université de Strasbourg
4. Tela Botanica
5. Université de Rennes 1
6. Université de Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier
7. Sorbonne Université
8. Société Nationale des Sciences Naturelles et Mathématiques de Cherbourg
9. Centre Informatique National de l'Enseignement Supérieur
10. Université Clermont Auvergne
11. Muséum d'histoire naturelle Philadelphie-Thomas de Gaillac
12. Jardin Botanique de la Ville de Lyon
13. Université de Montpellier
14. Université Lille 1 – Sciences et technologies
15. Université de Bourgogne
16. Institut Recherche et Développement
17. Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement
18. Université Claude-Bernard Lyon 1
19. Muséum d'histoire naturelle de La Rochelle
20. Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Dijon
21. Université Aix-Marseille
22. Muséum Aquarium de Nancy
23. Université de Lorraine
24. Université de Grenoble
25. Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Marseille
26. Musée d'histoire naturelle de Lille
27. Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Toulouse

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

Name of the Organisation's representative: Patricia Supply

Signature of the Organisation's representative: Patricia Supply Digitally signed
by Patricia Supply
(Signature)

Date: 18.11.2020

(Signature)
Date:
2020.11.18
08:05:20 +01'00'

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Meise Botanic Garden

Name of the Organisation's representative: Steven Dessen

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 4/11/2020

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Royal Museum for Central Africa

Name of the Organisation's representative: Guido Gryseels, Director General

Signature of the Organisation's representative: 8000795313 Digitally signed by
800079531388
88 Gryseels Gryseels Guido
Date: 2021.03.04
Guido 11:26:35 +01'00' 04/03/2021

Date:

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Natural History Museum, UK

Name of the Organisation's representative: DTJ Littlewood, Executive Director of Science

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 15 January 2021

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Michelle J. Price

Signature of the Organisation's representative: Michelle Price

Date: 1 December 2020

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation:

Naturhistorisches Museum Wien / Museum of Natural History Vienna

Name of the Organisation's representative: Dr. Katrin Vohland

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: _____

NATURHISTORISCHES MUSEUM
GENERALDIREKTION
A-1010 Wien, Burgring 7

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Dr. Maurice Hoffmann

Signature of the Organisation's representative: **RESEARCH INSTITUTE
NATURE AND FOREST**

Date: _____

Maurice
Hoffmann
(Signature)

 Digitaal ondertekend door
Maurice Hoffmann
(Signature)
Datum: 2020.11.10
21:07:43 +01'00'

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Université libre de Bruxelles

Name of the Organisation's representative: Daniele Carati

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 09/11/2020

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Jan Mees

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 18/11/2020

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Royal Zoological Society of Antwerp

Name of the Organisation's representative: Zjef Pereboom

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Zjef Pereboom', written over a light grey rectangular background.

Date: 16/03/2021

Name of the Signatory Organisation: **Université de Namur ASBL**

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Naji Habra, Rector

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 19/01/2021

In the Presence of

Pr. Frédéric Silvestre _____

In charge of the DiSSCo Project implementation and Member of the Institute of Life-Earth-Environment (ILEE)

Date: The 6th of January 2021

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: FU ZE BGBM

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Dr. Thomas Borsch
Kanzlerin FUB Direktor BGBM

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: 07.12.2020

Hier Text eingeben

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Center of Natural History

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Dr. Alexander Haas

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 4. November 2020

Name of the Signatory Organisation:

Museum für Naturkunde Berlin – Leibniz-Institut für Evolutions- und Biodiversitätsforschung
Invalidenstraße 43, 10115 Berlin

Name of the Organisation's representative:

Prof. Johannes Vogel, Ph.D.
General Director

Stephan Junker
Managing Director

Date: 14.01.2021

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Zoological Research Museum A. Koenig (ZFMK)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Dr. Bernhard Misof

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: Nov 18th, 2020

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttgart

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Dr. Lais Krogmann

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 3.11.20

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Senckenberg Gesellschaft für Naturforschung

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. Volker Mosbrugger

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Name of the Organisation's representative: Jan Henning Fahnster

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: November 9th, 2020

For country-level Consortia

[COUNTRY NAME]

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Hungarian Natural History Museum

Name of the Organisation's representative: Zsolt Bernert

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: Budapest, 14th January 2021

The Signatory Organisation represents the [COUNTRY NAME] national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. [Name of national consortium member organisation]
2. [Name of national consortium member organisation]
3. [Name of national consortium member organisation]
4. [Name of national consortium member organisation]

...

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation:
Musée National d'Histoire Naturelle de Luxembourg

Name of the Organisation's representative:
Alain Faber

Alain Faber
Directeur du Musée national
d'histoire naturelle

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date:

30 11 2020

Poland

Name of the Signatory Organisation: University of Warsaw

Name of the Organisation's representative: prof. Zygmunt Lalak

Signature of the Organisation's representative: _____

Date: _____

The Signatory Organisation represents the Polish national Consortium of the following Organisations:

1. University of Warsaw, represented by Vice-rector, prof. Zygmunt Lalak
2. Museum and Institute of Zoology PAS, represented by Director, prof. Tomasz Mazgajski

Zygmunt
Lalak; UW

Elektronicznie
podpisany przez
Zygmunt Lalak; UW
Data: 2021.03.05
16:47:31 +01'00'

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh

Name of the Organisation's representative: Professor Pete Hollingsworth, Director of Science and Deputy Keeper

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Pete Hollingsworth', written in a cursive style.

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 01.02.2021

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof Alexandre Antonelli

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 7/1/21

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Generaldirektion der Staatl.
Naturwissenschaftl. Sammlungen Bayerns
Menzinger Str. 71, 80638 München

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. Dr. Gerhard Haszprunar

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 11. Feb. 2021

Israel

Name of the Signatory Organisation: “Israel Natural Science Collections Consortium” (“INSCC”)

Name of the Organisation’s representative: The National Natural History Collection, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem,

Signature of the Organisation’s representative: _____

Dr. Pablo Kizelsztein
Director
The Authority for Research & Development
The Hebrew University of Jerusalem

Date: 10/10/2021

The Signatory Organisation represents the “Israel Natural Science Collections Consortium” (“INSCC”) of the following Organisations:

- (i) The National Natural History Collection, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem
- (ii) Beit Margolin Zoological Collection – Oranim, Academic College Education,
- (iii) Geological Survey of Israel,
- (iv) University of Haifa – The Research Authority representing the Natural Science Collections.

This Memorandum of Understanding includes seven (7) Articles and three (3) Annexes, signed, by the duly authorised undersigned representatives in [39] identical original copies. One copy is retained by each of the Signatories and one copy is forwarded to the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office for its acknowledgement and further relations at the following address, that will retain it:

DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office
c/o Dimitrios Koureas
Naturalis Biodiversity Center
Darwinweg 2, 2333 CR Leiden
The Netherlands

Name of the Signatory Daniela Zingg

Name of the legal representative: musnatcoll

Signature of the legal representative: D Zingg

Date: 9th March 2022

Name of the Signatory Peter Wandeler

Name of the legal representative musnatcoll

Signature of the legal representative: P. Wandeler

Date: 9th March 2022

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw-
en Visserijonderzoek (EVILVO)

Name of the Organisation's representative: Joris Rebaes

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date:

11/6/2021

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: University of Leuven

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof. dr. Joris Vandendriessche

Signature of the Organisation's representative: Joris Digitally signed by Joris

Date:

Vandendriessche
(Signature)

Vandendriessche (Signature)
Date: 2022.01.19 10:29:23 +01'00'

19 January 2022

For individual organisations and CETAF

Name of the Signatory Organisation: UNIVERSITEIT GENT

Name of the Organisation's representative: Prof FREDDY MORTIER

Signature of the Organisation's representative:

Date: 4-6 - 2021

Head of Entity
University Museums
and Archives.

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
ON
FORMATION OF THE EUROPEAN CONSORTIUM
FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE
DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM OF SCIENTIFIC COLLECTIONS (DiSSCo)

ANNEX A
DiSSCo high-level summary of concept and approach

Natural science collections are an integral part of the global natural and cultural capital. They include hundreds of millions of animals, plants, fossils, rocks, minerals and meteorites, which account for **55% of the natural sciences collections globally** and represent **80% of the world bio- and geo-diversity**. Data derived from these collections underpin countless innovations, including tens of thousands of scholarly publications and official reports (used to support legislative and regulatory processes relating to health, food, security, sustainability and environmental change); inventions and products critical to our bio-economy; databases, maps and descriptions of scientific observations; instructional material for students, as well as educational material for the public.

In the last couple of decades, we have witnessed great changes in the way we work in biodiversity science. Remote sensing, rapid identification and molecular approaches allow us to efficiently monitor the changing world around us and understand the cause of those changes. Advances of digital, genomic and information technologies enable natural science collections to provide discoveries and ask for new collection types and attributes while fostering the development of new approaches to face the urgent societal challenges. As the volume and diversity of information deriving from natural science collections are exponentially increasing, so is the need for adequate infrastructures that go further than providing access to the different data classes. **A holistic approach is required, which will effectively underpin the entire research lifecycle and provide access to mass, linked, reliable and precise data.**

A pan-European research infrastructure is urgently needed to solve the current limitations for the use of the data and related expertise contained by the natural science collections, largely caused by the

still highly fragmented landscape in Europe and the very low level of digitisation. A pan-European research initiative, as impersonated by DiSSCo, enables faster delivery of information, widens the community of scientific users and broadens usage in general.

DiSSCo enables European natural science collections to operate as a versatile and integrated system of distributed nodes. The new research infrastructure **unifies access to information, provides new linked data associated with collections, and drives policy and process harmonisation**. As a result, the new RI achieves the economies of scope and scale necessary to maximise impact on science and society. Through digitisation, aggregation and linkage of European collections, critical new insights will enable scientists to address some of the world's greatest challenges.

The key high-level objectives of DiSSCo include:

- Bringing scientific collections to the information age, investing in a linked open data approach;
- Investing in balanced multi-modal access to collections;
- Improving researchers' capacity to use collection information to tackle complex scientific challenges;
- Supporting the interplay of social and cultural aspects of collection data;
- Developing and implementing targeted joint research agendas;
- Identifying collection data at European level and improving curation efficiency;
- Building and supporting paths to industrial innovation;
- Enhancing digital skills and competencies, tooling-up researchers to navigate the big data domain; and
- Engaging with society, providing alternative ways of benefiting from the national investments to collections.

DiSSCo will provide a set of four service classes available for a wide range of users: (i) Physical (transnational) and digital (virtual) access to collections; (ii) Joint research programming for data-driven scientific innovation; (iii) Training, support and engagement, and (iv) Policy harmonisation.

Service Deliverables

DiSSCo aims to support fluent and permanent collaboration and interoperability across all European natural science collections and to establish a model for unified collection access, which can be expanded to a global scale, as other non-European regions promote in parallel infrastructures. Despite the homogeneous and comprehensive access to data, different user communities have specific

requirements that are to be met with six key services provided during the operational phase.

Service deliverable	Short description
Unified platform policy	DiSSCo will be developed based on a common comprehensive policy corpus agreed to be implemented across all DiSSCo facilities. These policies will be underpinned by (i) open access principles, including FAIR principles, (ii) clear incentive schemes for citation and attribution, and (iii) thematic prioritisation, for the digitisation of the distributed collections. Furthermore, these policies will extend to the development of joint research programming activities across all its members.
Unified community of expertise	DiSSCo will facilitate collaborative research by enabling consistent pan-European digital access and data curation rights for research and curatorial and technical staff from all collections. DiSSCo will also create an integrated registry of experts with expertise linked to European collections.
Unified access to collections	Access to collections is a centrepiece service for DiSSCo. Services will be provided for both physical and virtual modes of access. DiSSCo will support a transnational access programme and couple this with comprehensive virtual (digital) access service. DiSSCo will deliver an information system which offers, to the fullest extent possible, consistent access for all authorised researchers not only to be able to access data from any collection but also contribute to the curation and improvement of these data. A European Collections Data Portal will enable direct and open access to the integrated database.

Unified knowledge graph

The engineering of the DiSSCo knowledge graph will bring together digital information and assets from all participating institutions, with institutional management systems for collections, laboratories and other facilities remaining the persistent repository for these data, and will additionally include further digital knowledge derived from graphing these data objects and resolving identities between multiple institutions. The entire graph will be navigable as a set of interconnected rich data records.

Unified web services

The DiSSCo unified knowledge graph will be accessible via search, visualisation and download services to support efficient researcher access to data. DiSSCo will ensure that the resulting linked open data (LOD) is fully accessible for exploration, mining and semantic inference within European high-performance computing infrastructures, and fit for use by other European infrastructures (e.g. LifeWatch) and contributing to global infrastructures (e.g. GBIF).

Unified capacity development

A consistent pan-European approach to training will simplify accreditation of skills and enable appropriate mechanisms to be put in place for user access rights around DiSSCo data. The approach will also support the development of European collections personnel as a unified community of expertise and excellence.

User communities

- **Research communities and individual researchers** in Environmental/natural sciences (incl. taxonomists, ecologists, bio-informaticians, conservationists, ethno-botanists, geneticists, chemists);
- **Virtual Research Environments (VREs)** users, providers and stakeholders;
- **Citizen scientists and naturalists** and coordinators of citizen science projects in biodiversity;
- **Object/Data holders** (partners to the project, external repositories, potential users of other domains);
- **Aggregators of taxonomic/biodiversity data** (e.g. GBIF, EoL) and Indexing agents (e.g. CoL, IPNI, ZooBank);
- **Policy and decision-makers** in governmental and non-governmental organisations;
- **Education organisations** including vocational and academic teachers and students;
- **Industry stakeholders** including service providers, industrial devices/technology producers;
- **European Research Infrastructures** (incl. LifeWatch, ELIXIR, MIRRI, EPOS, and E-RIHS).

Maturity and sustainability

DiSSCo is built on top of a strong, stable and cohesive European network of natural sciences collections-based institutions (CETAF) and benefits from the accumulated experience of several EC-funded projects such as SYNTHESYS I-III, EDIT, ViBRANT and pro-iBiosphere. **Together, this cumulative experience provides a robust corpus of technical, governance and socio-cultural feasibility reports and studies, that drives the development and operation of the new Research Infrastructure.**

DiSSCo is uniquely placed among other distributed networks or infrastructures, as **the entirety of the participating facilities have secured long-term financial support through governmental statutory funding** and already successfully operate in the context of regional and/or national strategic priorities.

European Research Infrastructures: Landscape view

In the European landscape of environmental Research Infrastructures, different projects and landmarks describe services that aim at aggregating, monitoring, analysing and modelling geo and bio-diversity information. The effectiveness of these services, however, is based on the **quality and availability of primary reference data that today is scattered and incomplete**. DiSSCo provides the required taxonomic, bio-geographical and species trait data at the level of precision and accuracy required to enable research for tackling grand societal challenges.

DiSSCo fills a significant gap in the landscape of European research infrastructures. In the wider European RI landscape DiSSCo acts as the missing reliable block of the value chain where services and final products need to be grounded for adequately monitoring and modelling the geo- and bio-sphere.

The DiSSCo preparatory and transition phases are planned between 2018 and 2023 (Innovation and Consolidation programmes):

Innovation programme: Refinement of technical design; deployment of pilot portal and service test beds; update of business plan; contact-building with industrial stakeholders; technical innovation for mass scale digitisation, automation, robotics, and data models.

Consolidation programme: Refinement of governance structure; preparation for setting-up of legal entity; communication and capacity building; update of business plan; harmonisation of nodes policies and processes (incl. access and training); site selection and staff recruitment; development of national-level collection and investment strategies.

2024 -

Construction phase: Implementation of national/regional investment plans for infrastructure upgrades and large scale digitisation programmes; application of joint DiSSCo programmes and policies, quality control and risk management; establishment of regional/thematic hubs; active membership; construction of the DiSSCo Hub (including all services).

2024 onwards

Operational phase: Full deployment of operations and services; first full evaluation process; review of organisation and business model; full scale operations.

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ANNEX B

Governance, management and participation model for DiSSCo implementation and operation

1. Foreword

1.1. Context and references

This document proposes the key governing and management bodies of the DiSSCo research infrastructure, the role of advisory committees and the relationship between them. Furthermore, the document briefly calls upon procedural and policy issues that cross-cut DiSSCo infrastructure organisation, as well as the functional relations with distributed nodes. Finally, it recommends a participation and contribution model and advises on viable mechanisms for reaching consensus and conflict resolution. The herein included propositions are subject to approval by the DiSSCo consortium.

For the development of the governance model the following have been considered and evaluated:

- a. Governance and management models of other ESFRI projects and landmarks;
- b. Recommendations proposed by the OECD Global Science Forum group of experts on 17 July 2013;
- c. Specificities and requirements linked to the operation of a distributed research infrastructure (as defined by OECD/GSF);
- d. Related reports from project deliverables (EC and nationally funded) (incl. EDIT and pro-iBiosphere) [part of the DiSSCo Design/Feasibility Study];
- e. Governance and management models of supporting organisations as the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF) and affiliated networks, including the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF);
- f. Recommendations included in the Report of the Implementation Group to the ESFRI Forum (November 2012);
- g. CoPoRi project public reports on best practices for development of research infrastructures in Europe;
- h. RAMIRI project public handbook;
- i. DiSSCo research infrastructure Scientific Case (2017);
- j. DiSSCo research infrastructure Design Study (incl. technical design) (2017);
- k. DiSSCo governance and management model (2017);
- l. DiSSCo Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) Terms of Reference (2019);
- m. DiSSCo Technical Advisory Board (TAB) Terms of Reference (2019);
- n. DiSSCo General Assembly Terms of Reference (2020);
- o. Conceptual design blueprint for the DiSSCo digitisation infrastructure (2020);

- p. Funders Forum RoP (2020);
- q. Stakeholders Forum RoP (2021).

1.2. Objectives

The proposed model aims at:

- a. Optimal delivery of all central DiSSCo research infrastructure services;
- b. Achieving the maximum possible inclusion of and balance between member states and associated countries (through participation of national facilities) in the decision-making processes;
- c. Ensuring transparent and fair procedures, with clearly indicated accountable parties, defining and formalising their mandate;
- d. Minimising the administrative overheads, without compromising the integrity of the governing procedures;
- e. Maintaining adequate flexibility to adapt to future change of needs, including fast expansion of membership or widening of scope, taking into account the different stages of the RI lifecycle;
- f. Setting up well-defined consensus reaching and conflict resolution mechanisms;
- g. Ensure optimal delivery of the DiSSCo services.

1.3. Succession of governance and management structures and time frames

The development (preparatory and transition phases) as well as construction and operation phases of DiSSCo are linked to distinct and succeeding phases that require different governance and management models. Seamless transition from one structure to the other is instrumental.

The document describes the governance structures for each of the distinct phases as follows (Figure 1.1):

- a. Bid development phase;
- b. Preparatory and transition phase;
- c. Construction and Operational Phase.

The hereinafter different governance models will succeed each other following clearly defined transitional periods and in accordance with the development of DiSSCo (Table 1.1)

DiSSCo phase	Governance and management structure in place	Expected timeframe
Bid development	Bid development (Standard project management model)	2016 -2018
Preparatory and transition phase	Interim Governance and management	2018 – 2023
Construction phase	Transition modalities	2024 –
Operational phase	Operational phase Governance and management	2025 -

Table 1.1. Timeframe and matching of governance and management structures with the different DiSSCo phases. Highlighted cells correspond to the critical phases and their corresponding governance structures.

2. Interim Governance and management models

2.1. Definition and timing

The interim Governance and management model covers the preparatory and transition phases until the formulation of the legal entity of the research infrastructure. Special arrangements for facilitating the transition to the governance model of the operational phase will be agreed at a subsequent phase. Preparatory and transition work during this phase will be handled as a series of programmes and projects.

2.2. Membership levels

2.2.1. MEMBERS

Members may be any of the following entities who have signed the European MoU:

- National consortia of natural science collection-based organisations;
- Single nature collections-based organisations from countries that have not set up a national consortium;
- The Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF)

Members participate in the General Assembly with one vote. Additional conditions and procedures for application procedure shall be set out in the Terms of Reference for the General Assembly.

2.2.2. ASSOCIATE MEMBERS

Associated members may be any of the following entities who have signed the European MoU:

- National consortia of natural science collection-based organisations;
- Single nature collections-based organisations from countries that have not set up a national consortium;

Associate members participate in the General Assembly without voting rights. Additional conditions and application procedure shall be set out in the Terms of Reference for the General Assembly.

2.2.3. OBSERVERS

Observers may be any of the following entities:

- National consortia of natural science collection-based organisations that have expressed in writing an interest in becoming a member or associate member;
- Governmental entities that have expressed in writing a commitment to provide financial support to DiSSCo;
- Entities with a European or international dimension, with a mission and objectives that are deemed pertinent to DiSSCo.

Observers participate in the General Assembly without voting rights. Additional conditions and application procedure shall be set out in the Terms of Reference for the General Assembly.

2.3. Governing Bodies

2.3.1. GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The DiSSCo General Assembly (GA) is the DiSSCo preparatory and transition phases ultimate decision-making body and is composed of representatives of the Members, Associate Members and

Observers. The GA oversees the progress of the different work programmes and associated projects under the two key stages of developing DiSSCo.

Duties and Powers

- Adopts strategic plans (technical, scientific and administrative);
- Approves statutes and bylaws as needed
- Approves the preparatory and transition phases budget;
- Approves annual or interim accounts audit report;
- Approves the annual reports (technical, scientific and administrative);
- Approves Coordinator's annual report;
- Approves changes in the membership;
- Approves bid development and other funding and financing actions for DiSSCo;
- Approves changes in the DiSSCo financial/contribution model;
- Oversees performance of the Coordination office;
- Appoints the DiSSCo preparatory, transition and construction phase coordinator and the members of the Interim Coordination Office;
- Appoints DiSSCo programmes and project boards;
- Establishes non-executive advisory bodies, and;
- Signs-off the deliverables of DiSSCo-related programmes and projects.

Membership

All Consortium members fully participate in the GA with one delegate. Consortium member delegates have full voting rights. Associated members participate in the GA with one representative and with no voting rights. A chair and a vice-chair of the GA is elected during the inaugural¹ GA meeting. Membership is reviewed on an ad-hoc basis, subject to fulfilment of the membership (including associated membership) requirements.

Mode of operation

GA convenes regularly on an annual basis. Meetings are convened by the GA chair with contributions from the DiSSCo coordinator and organised by the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office. Order of business is communicated prior to the meetings. Detailed meeting minutes are kept and circulated to all stakeholders and publicly. Further details are set out in the Terms of Reference for the GA..

2.4. Coordination and Support Office (CSO)

During the DiSSCo preparatory, transition and construction phases, a Coordination and Support Office (CSO) will operate. The role of CSO is to undertake work relevant to the implementation of the agreed upon work programme under the preparatory, transition and construction stages.

The CSO will:

- Implement agreed upon KPIs and produce reports for the GA;
- Communicate progress of the project to all members, associated members and any national or European authority if requests so;
- Coordinate the development and implementation of projects relevant to the development of the DiSSCo RI;
- Spec, resource tasks for internally managed programmes and projects developed under these programmes;

¹ The inaugural meeting is convened by the DiSSCo proposal preparation phase steering committee chair.

- Draft agreements and administer contracts (in collaboration with nodes and facilities) as needed;
- Spec and oversee procurement of software, hardware and services for the development of the DiSSCo technical infrastructure;
- Develop in-house expertise to underpin its technical, policy, capacity building, and management responsibilities;
- Undertake software engineering tasks towards the development of the DiSSCo RI;
- Compile policy drafts and organise consultation rounds;
- Monitor the progress of policy, process and operations harmonisation across all participating facilities;
- Provide expert advice to facilities and nodes as per their request and available capacity;
- Outreach the CSO achievements and the DiSSCo progress;
- Undertake other tasks, subject to separate GA mandates.

2.5. **Coordinator**

The DiSSCo preparatory, transition and construction phases' coordinator, assigned by the GA, will take responsibility for the implementation of the work programmes relevant to the development of the infrastructure and the transition to the operational phase. The coordinator is supported by the personnel of the CSO. Deputy coordinators can be appointed by the GA as needed.

Responsibilities of the Coordinator:

- Oversees the operation of the CSO and manages all allocated to the office personnel;
- Leads on the development of funding bids in support of the development of the DiSSCo RI;
- Contributes to (or leads) DiSSCo programme boards and overlooks relevant work projects;
- Leads on activities relevant to the expansion of the DiSSCo consortium;
- Reports on regular basis to the GA and the chair and co-chair, and provides advice on course of actions, as per their request;
- Maintains a high-level understanding of the overall progress and recommends correction/mitigation actions;
- Participates ex-officio to GA meetings;
- Represents DiSSCo at senior level to public and private stakeholders and meetings;
- Acts as the contact point for all DiSSCo full and associated members.
- Provide a secretariat to the General Assembly in accordance with the Terms of Reference for the General Assembly.

2.6. **Scientific (SAB) and Technical (TAB) Advisory Boards**

The Scientific and Technical Advisory Boards are standing DiSSCo Committees.. The SAB/TAB provide expert opinion on issues related to the scientific mission of the research infrastructure and to its technical architecture and overall approach. The SAB/TAB provide expert opinion to all bodies of DiSSCo, including the GA and the CSO. Members of SAB and TAB are appointed directly by the GA.

2.7. **Working Groups (Work packages)**

DiSSCo enters the preparatory phase for the construction of the research infrastructure with a clear

and timely work programme. Following the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) a set of Working groups is expected to undertake work and to provide assessment to the CSO in the different areas of priority for the development of the research infrastructure. The working groups operate under the supervision of the coordinator. Membership of the working groups is proposed to the coordinator by the Scientific and/or Technical Advisory Boards. The coordinator approves the membership.

2.8. Financial contribution model of members

The preparatory and transition hinges on national and other stakeholders' financial contributions. The estimated capital value (incl. all pooled assets) and project implementation costs are presented in the financial feasibility study and DiSSCo budget. For the aforementioned period (projected between 2018 and 2024) DiSSCo employs a simple and transparent contribution model (in-cash and in-kind).

2.9. Interim governance model overview

3. Transition period modalities

A critical task for the transition period is the transformation of the interim governance structure into the operational governance structure upon an established legal entity.

The GA will be accountable for a smooth and efficient transition. The CSO will propose adoption of RI arrangements (including technical, administrative, governing and financial aspects) that will need approval and adoption by the GA. Once approved, new terms will operate under the new adopted Governance and management model.

4. Construction & Operational phase - Membership, governance, management and advisory bodies

At the time of drafting this section, the exact legal framework chosen for the long-term operation of DiSSCo is yet unknown. A number of options are available in the context of the characteristics of DiSSCo, such as a collaboration agreement; an intergovernmental organisation; a national vehicle (e.g. a limited liability company or a Belgian AISBL); memorandum of understanding or an ERIC (a European Research Infrastructure Consortium).

The final choice of the legal framework for DiSSCo is likely to impact the exact form of governance, the management structure and membership options. However, it is envisaged that the basic structure, as described in the sections below, will not be affected significantly by the choice of the legal entity, although a degree of tweaking and adjustment may be needed.

The following sections are agreed upon and proposed by the Signatories for the construction of the DiSSCo legal entity and to be part of its statutes and bylaws.

4.1. Research infrastructure siting

4.1.1. Host of the coordination office/Hub (CCO)

The CCO retains a significant role in the development and provision of DiSSCo services. The CCO will make use of distributed resources, but also maintain a strong physical presence.

During the initial stages of the preparatory phase, the General Assembly will assess all available and feasible options and decide on the siting of the coordination office. A list of pre-defined criteria can be used and weighted (Table 4.1).

4.1.1.1. Siting criteria

No.	Title
C1	Commitment to DiSSCo by the Country and potential hosting facility
C2	Ability and commitment to pay host premium
C3	Existing Node/Facility investments in digital access activities
C4	Availability of appropriate human resources with relevant expertise
C5	Accessibility

Table 4.1. Criteria for the selection of the country and place to host centrally administered operations of the DiSSCo Central Coordination Office.

4.1.2. Financial contribution model

DiSSCo predicates its operational longevity on its Member contributions. Its financial model is split between a development and an operating budget. The development budget includes all costs related to the preparatory and transition phases of the new research infrastructure, as well as to the development of new services during the operational phase. The operating budget cover for all cost centres relevant for the construction phase and to the provision of agreed upon services.

Members of DiSSCo pay an annual fee (based on a common model) to sustain and operate the DiSSCo research infrastructure. The fee will cover the provision of the following service classes: (i) physical and virtual access services, (ii) Data portal and digitisation services, (iii) Training and support services and (iv) Joint research programming services. Furthermore, DiSSCo Members will jointly provision for all other operating costs and administration.

4.1.3. Contribution algorithm

The size of the fees for each Member is based on a contribution algorithm to come in effect after by when the DiSSCo legal entity starts to operate. The contribution algorithm may consider (i) the size of collections at national level (as represented by facilities in the national node), (ii) a 5-year averaged Eurostat Index of GDP, (iii) the estimated user demand for access per member country or any other relevant index. Final decisions on the applicable model will be taken during the preparatory and transition phases by the Interim governing bodies.

4.1.4. Ability to pay

Members of the Consortium shall consider all special and temporary national and international circumstances that might reduce the ability of a DiSSCo Member to pay its membership. Special arrangements can be agreed by the DiSSCo GA to levy a Member's annual subscription dues, whilst the Member retains full membership privileges.

4.1.5. Host premium

During all phases of DiSSCo RI, the country/facility hosting the coordination office sitting(s) will pay a host premium to cover the CCO operating costs. These costs include the provision of a fully functional and serviced office space. The costs can be contributed in-cash or in-kind. The host premium cannot be accounted as part of the Member contribution fees and should be an additional contribution to any other contractual arrangement.

4.1.6. Reference currency

The reference currency of DiSSCo will be set as the national currency of the country to host the DiSSCo legal entity. Monetisation of IKC and all ICC shall be agreed upon and accounted for in the DiSSCo reference currency.

4.2. Modes of contributions

4.2.1. In-kind contributions (IKC)

Conversely to cash contributions (ICC), in-kind contributions (IKC) represent the provision of goods or services, valued in monetary terms and accounted for as part of the Member's contribution to the budget. In-kind contributions will be provided by DiSSCo Members towards the development and operation of the infrastructure. In-kind contributions include the provision of facilities, technical infrastructure or components, as well as personnel time (workforce). The amount of the contribution will be accounted according to the rules agreed upon by the members. DiSSCo governing bodies sets clear rules for IKC cycles, through service-level-agreements, which include: (i) Definition of IKC for each task and provider, (ii) Crediting of the value, (iii) Rules and processes of delivery through IKC Agreements (IKCA) between the provider and the DiSSCo CCO, and (iv) final assessment/delivery report.

4.2.2. In-cash contributions (ICC)

In-cash contributions, pledged by a DiSSCo Member, will need to be clearly defined in terms of (i) amount, (ii) mode and frequency of payout. A member can identify and commit in cash contributions from multiple national sources, including, but not limited to, core governmental budgets and institutional (facility) / Node (national research infrastructures) budgets.

The total amount of financial contribution from a member is accounted as the sum of the ICC pledge and the monetarised equivalent of the IKC (per IKC agreement) commitment.

4.3. Review policies

The operational phase of the DiSSCo research infrastructure will be reviewed on a regular basis. The following review mechanisms will come into place.

- (i) Annual reviews of the modus operandi of the established service-level-agreements (or similar mutual contracts) between the DiSSCo RI and distributed national facilities. Part of these reviews is to assess the implementation and valuation of national in-kind contributions and the effectiveness of the DiSSCo services for the distributed facilities.
- (ii) Five-yearly reviews of the full operations and business arrangements of the DiSSCo RI. These reviews serve to inform the General Assembly, and will assist in negotiating the next term of Member financial contributions. As such, these five-year reviews will be reported at least one year before the end of each five-year budget cycle. This means that the first review report will be submitted by the end of the third year of the first five-year cycle. This also helps to inform the members about the initial performance of DiSSCo in its operational phase.
- (iii) Decadal additional review focus, giving specific attention to the question if the DiSSCo RI must continue according to the current joint Member's agreement (as per the DiSSCo Statutes), or that a major change should be considered. This might imply a change of operational objectives, a major upgrade, or decommissioning if appropriate.
- (iv) Transfer of authority

a. Premise and approach

As a distributed infrastructure, DiSSCo's success hinges on the performance of its own

central infrastructure services, as well as on the capacity to coordinate and harmonise certain operational and policy aspects of its nodes. Specifically, DiSSCo acknowledges that:

- (i) Natural Science Collection organisations in Europe are institutions with an extended range of scientific and societal remits. As such, they serve multiple socio-economic roles at local, national or regional level;
- (ii) The development and operation of DiSSCo is relevant to only a fraction of their mission;
- (iii) For DiSSCo to deliver the quality and robustness of its services to the European and international scientific community, it is imperative that decisions over certain internal institutional operations (and policies) are transferred to DiSSCo central coordination;
- (iv) To facilitate this process, a clear and transparent list of the operational and policy aspects of DiSSCo facilities, that will be centrally administered, will need to be agreed, as part of the participation agreement to the DiSSCo consortium and legal entity;
- (v) Clear conflict resolution mechanisms need to be defined and agreed to resolve issues relevant to the decision-making procedures.
- (vi) For the successful construction of the research infrastructure it is expected that all Members (at facility level) shall also comply to this transfer of powers for the full duration of the preparatory, transition and construction phase as well as the operational phase, subject to any amendments by the General Assembly.

Based on the above, the following table provides a list of common institutional operations and policies, the harmonisation of which will be critical for the delivery of the DiSSCo services.

Policies	
DiSSCo will become a pan-European infrastructure and policy corpus. This will be a set of policy principles that will enable consolidation and harmonisation across the DiSSCo nodes, as well as the facilitation of DiSSCo service offering. Node collection facilities will incorporate these principles into institutional-level policies within pre-agreed timeframes. Exceptions to the implementation of principles deriving from the common policy framework will apply in circumstances where national regulations or legislation is mandating a different approach.	
i	Collection access and Information policies <i>Adoption of common information management procedures, collection access policies and unit cost calculation methodologies. Implementation of common visitor procedures.</i>
ii	Laboratory/equipment access policies <i>Adoption of common laboratory and other analytical equipment policies and lab-derived data management policies.</i>

iii	<p>Intellectual property policies</p> <p>European harmonisation of Intellectual Property policies for data/media derived from the study of/access to collections.</p>
iv	<p>Data management policies</p> <p><i>Incorporation of common policy frameworks for data archiving and preservation, capture of metadata at record and dataset level,</i></p>
v	<p>Digital skills and competencies frameworks</p> <p><i>Harmonisation of data skills and competencies frameworks at node and facility-level.</i></p>
<p>Operations/Systems/Programmes</p> <p>Harmonisation and alignment of the below mentioned distributed operations and scientific data systems are instrumental for the delivery of the DiSSCo objectives and successful provision of its services. Collection facilities will work towards commonly agreed upon technical implementations in the areas below.</p>	
vi	<p>Collection management systems</p> <p><i>Incorporation of technical provisions (incl. harmonised data models, ingestion and output mechanisms) to enable interoperability across collection management systems.</i></p>
vi i	<p>Media management systems</p> <p><i>Alignment to common data models that follow agreed upon metadata standards. Copyright and License management. Open standardised web services.</i></p>
vi ii	<p>Laboratory information management systems</p> <p><i>Capture of analytical actions in a standardised manner. Application of common data models for output. Integration with collection management systems and interoperability with DiSSCo Data portal.</i></p>
ix	<p>Data curation workflows and procedures</p> <p><i>Standardisation and alignment, at European level, of data curation workflows and procedures. Unified specimen persistent identifiers.</i></p>
x	<p>Digitisation workflows and technical specifications of digitisation outputs</p> <p><i>Conform to Imaging minimum viable product requirements; Scientific data extraction procedures; Implementation of common digitisation cost-book models.</i></p>
xi	<p>Digitisation programmes alignment</p> <p><i>Conform with taxonomic/geographic complementarity between facility- and node-level digitisation</i></p>

	<i>programme; Uptake of digitisation tasks on an ad-hoc basis.</i>
xi i	Web services common framework <i>Incorporation of access and functional requirements of facility-level web services.</i>
xi ii	Common Persistent Identifiers (PID) Systems <i>Conform with commonly agreed PID systems implementation and facility-level PID record information.</i>
xi v	Federated authentication and authorisation systems for researchers/curators <i>Participate in federated authentication and authorisation systems.</i>
x v	Capacity building <i>Implementation of mid- and long-term digital skills and competencies development activities. Participation in European training programmes for researchers and curators.</i>

b. Implementation mechanisms

Seamless operation of the DiSSCo research infrastructure is predicated on the **policy and operational synchronisation of all the DiSSCo nodes, at facility-level**. To ensure optimal harmonisation of the distributed facilities, DiSSCo General Assembly will make use of a set of instruments to propose or mandate centrally-taken decisions across all members, at the facility level. These instruments, which will be legally arranged in mutual service-level-agreements (or another contract), are as follows:

Decision type	Level of mandate
Communication	<i>Good to do / Best practice</i> Communications propose modes of operation, technical solutions or policy frameworks as best practices for inclusion at Node and Facility level. Communications do not mandate any action, they do, however, indicate the future direction of the research infrastructure. Communications can have a wider (outside the research infrastructure) impact and value as public statements or positions.
Recommendation	<i>Should do</i> Recommendations represent a stronger decision type than communications. Nodes and facilities should consider ways of implementing a recommendation. Nodes and their facilities should put in place mechanisms for gradually adapting to the recommendation. Implementation of a recommendation across Nodes and Facilities is monitored, but not enforced.

Instruction	<i>Must do</i> <p>Instructions are progressively issued, following communications/recommendations and are subject to prior successful consultation and agreement between DiSSCo members at GA level. Instructions describe minimum actions to be taken by all Members, at facility or Node level, to enable the uninterrupted provision of all DiSSCo services. Instructions will conform to standard minimum requirements, including, but not limited to, detailed rationale, action plan, resourcing issues, and date of entry to force.</p>
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MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
ON
FORMATION OF THE EUROPEAN CONSORTIUM
FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE
DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM OF SCIENTIFIC COLLECTIONS (DiSSCo)

ANNEX C

Responsibilities and membership of the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office

Role and Responsibilities

The Coordination and Support Office (CSO) is responsible for the successful implementation of the agreed upon action plan.

In particular, the Coordination and Support Office:

- Implements the agreed action plan to the agreed standards and deadlines;
- Invites experts to form Working Groups and monitors their activity and outcomes;
- Drafts the agendas for the General Assembly meetings;
- Assesses the overall implementation progress;
- Coordinates the work of the National Nodes and provides guidance on an ad-hoc basis;
- Interacts with ESFRI officials in relation to ESFRI Roadmap issues and follow-up actions;
- Reviews the overall progress of efforts at national level;
- Liaises with all internal and external stakeholders as required;
- Represents the Consortium to external forums and stakeholders as required.

Composition

The Coordination and Support Office consists of the Coordinator (CO) and two deputy Coordinators (DCO). The Coordination and Support Office can appoint people to work on supporting tasks for the Coordination and Support Office in administration, governance and coordination.

The CSO is overall responsible for the implementation of the project tasks. It reports directly to the General Assembly and manages all human resources related to the implementation of the project. When required the CO or any of the DCOs may represent the Coordination and Support Office or the Consortium and acts as an ambassador of the project to identified stakeholders.

The CO is responsible for the process management. In consultation with the DCOs the CO sets a detailed planning for the remaining project runtime and ensures understanding of, and agreement on this planning among all partners and key stakeholders. The CO ensures timely delivery of each deliverable from the Working Groups, and National Nodes. The CO timely informs all of them about potential risks and bottlenecks regarding the working schedule and the means available to uphold it.

The CSO is responsible for a proper and transparent project administration. The CSO maintains the digital project environment used in DiSSCo. The CSO secures all input generated throughout the project in a way that is transparent and logical to project partners and stakeholders.

Further roles and responsibilities may be set out in the Terms of Reference for the General Assembly and related documents.